

exp(i Action) with V(x) and the Schrodinger Equation

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The form $\exp(i \text{Action})$ is often used as a propagator of solutions of the Schrödinger equation. In (1), $x(t) = Y/A(T) A(T-t) + X/A(T) A(t)$ ((1)) and this form is used in the Lagrangian to calculate $\text{Action} = \int dt (0,T) L$. (Here we have interchanged X and Y from the form in ((1)).) We argue that unless $X=A(T)$, this is not really a Lagrangian. In fact, X and A(T) are treated as independent in order to have $\exp(i \text{Action})$ satisfy the Schrodinger equation. In an earlier note (2), we examined the free particle case for which $\int (0,T) dt \frac{1}{2} m v^2 = \frac{1}{2} m \frac{X^2}{T}$. $\exp(i \frac{1}{2} m \frac{X^2}{T})$ has certain properties under the operations of d/dT and d/dX . In particular, $i d/dT \exp(i \text{Action}) = E \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i d/dX \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$. These values may be inserted into an energy conservation equation containing E and p and lead to a differential equation i.e. the Schrodinger equation (or Klein-Gordon equation in the relativistic case).

We argued in (2) that one may generalize the free particle Schrodinger equation by adding a potential $V(x)$ which is considered to be stochastic i.e. $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. In such a case, one has a momentum distribution $P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ instead of the free particle $\exp(ipx)$. In this note, we consider extending $\exp(i \frac{1}{2} m \frac{X^2}{T})$, the nonrelativistic $\exp(i \text{Action})$ to a full "Lagrangian". We point out that this is not really the Lagrangian because X and A(T) are considered to be independent which they are not. (A(t) is a solution of Newton's law.) Thus, we seek an object such that $i d/dT \text{object} + V(x) = -1/2m d/dX \text{object} * d/dX \text{object} + V(x)$. Here $V(x)$ is the potential which was added to the free particle Schrodinger equation as part of conservation of energy. We argue that $\exp(i \text{Action})$ where Action uses the full Lagrangian with the "form" ((1)) satisfies the Schrodinger equation.

Free Particle Case

In (2), we argued that $\exp(i \text{Action})$ with $\text{Action} = \frac{1}{2} m \frac{X^2}{T}$ for a free particle leads to: $i d/dT \exp(i \text{Action}) = E \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i d/dX \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$. E and p are classical values and so one may utilise a classical equation linking the two (i.e. conservation of energy) and convert it into a differential equation which represents a kind of fluctuation. In the nonrelativistic case, this is the Schrodinger equation i.e.

$$E = p^2 \quad \text{so} \quad i d/dT \exp(i \text{Action}) = -1/2m d/dX d/dX \exp(i \text{Action}) \quad ((2))$$

Given that this is a conservation of energy equation, one may postulate that adding $V(x)$ to the RHS of ((2)) yields the Schrodinger equation in the case of a potential.

The Case of a Potential V(x)

One may ask: How is the Schrodinger equation with V(x) related to the form $\exp(i \int \dots)$ which is not exactly $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ because X and T are independent? One may immediately see that:

$$i \frac{d}{dT} \exp\left(i \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[-V[XA(t)/A(T)] \right]\right) \text{ yields a term } V(x) \exp\left(i \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[V[XA(t)/A(T)] \right]\right) \quad ((3))$$

where $X=A(T)$. Thus, it seems that by extending the free particle action to a full Lagrangian albeit with $X/A(T)$ included such that X and A(T) are independent is a possible route to take. Essentially, one wishes to find:

$$i \frac{d}{dT} \text{object} = -1/2m \frac{d}{dX} \text{object} \cdot \frac{d}{dX} \text{object} + V(X) \quad ((4))$$

((3)) gives a factor which if included in "object" immediately eliminates V(X) on the RHS of ((4)). This also shows why V(x) enters with a -1 in the Lagrangian.

Consider now the "action" form:

$$\int_{(0,T)} dt \text{ Action} = \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[.5mXX / [A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA}{dt} \frac{dA}{dt} + V[XA(t)/A(T)] \right] \quad ((5))$$

$$i \frac{d}{dT} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = \exp(i \text{ Action}) \left\{ - .5m XX/[A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA}{dt(T)} \frac{dA}{dt(T)} + V(X) \right.$$

$$- \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[(-m) XX/[A(T)A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(T) \right.$$

$$\left. + \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[-XA(t)/[A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA(T)}{dt} \right] \right\} \quad ((6a))$$

$$\left(-i \frac{d}{dx} \right) \left(-i \frac{d}{dX} \right) = \text{square} \left\{ \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[mX/[A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t) - \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[-XA(t)/[A(T)A(T)] \frac{dA}{dT}(T) \right] \right\} \quad ((6b))$$

In order to equate ((6a)) and ((6b)) + V(x), we make use of:

$$\frac{d}{dt} [A(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t)] = \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t) + A(t) \frac{d}{dt} \frac{d}{dt} A(t) \quad ((7)) \quad \text{with } A(0)=0$$

Thus: $\int_{(0,T)} dt \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t)$ which appears in ((6a)) and ((6b)) may be replaced with:

$$\int_{(0,T)} dt \frac{dA}{dt}(t) \frac{dA}{dt}(t) = A(T) \frac{dA}{dT}(T) - 1/m \int_{(0,T)} dt \left[\frac{dV}{dy} [X/A(T)] \right] \quad ((8))$$

Thus, the second term on the RHS of ((8)) combines with the dV/dy term in both ((6a)) and ((6b)). Note that for a classical solution $X=A(T)$, but when d/dT and d/dX are taken X and $A(T)$ are independent. Thus, Newton's second law ((8)) seems to be violated during this fluctuation process which leads to the Schrodinger equation. The same issue, however, follows for Integral $\int dt V(x)$ in the Action as $V(x)$ is replaced with $V(X/A(T) A(t))$. If $X=A(T)$ this is the potential because $x=A(T)$, but when X and $A(T)$ vary independently, one veers away from the potential of the classical path. The same is true with $dV(x)/dx = dV(A(t)/dA(t) = dV(y)/dy X/A(t)$ where $y=A(t)X/A(T)$.

With ((8)), one may finally equate:

$$((6a)) = ((6b)) + V(x) \quad ((9))$$

One way to achieve ((9)) is to reimpose the constraint $A(T)=X$ after differentiation has occurred. This also applies in the free particle case where X and T in XX/T are independent variables before differentiation, but $XX/TT = vv$ where v =velocity is a constant after differentiation. In this scheme,

$$1/2m (-i\hbar/dX)(-i\hbar/dX) \text{ leads to } \hbar^2/2m dA/dt(T) dA/dt(T) \text{ while}$$

$i\hbar/dT$ leads to $i\hbar/2m dA/dt(T) dA/dt(T)$ as well because the Integral $\int dt A(t)dV/dy$ terms cancel.

Usually, in the literature one equates coefficients of powers of X , but here one does not know the form of the potential.

Thus, $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ using the full Action = $T-V$ with $x(t)=XA(t)/A(T)$ and then varying X and T independently is a solution of the Schrodinger equation containing $V(x)$.

Eigenfunction Expansion

Another approach to propagators is to consider the orthonormal complete set of solutions of:

$$i\hbar/dt W_n = [-1/2m d/dx d/dx + V(x)] W_n(x,t) \quad ((10))$$

Solutions are: $\exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$ where $W_n(x)$ is complete

If one considers $\exp[i \text{ Action}(T, X)]$ and sets T equal to a constant, then $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ should be:

$$\exp(i \text{ Action}) = \sum_n a_n(t) W_n(x) \quad ((11))$$

For this to satisfy the Schrodinger equation, the coefficients of $W_n(x)$ must be 0 because $W_n(x)$'s are independent. Thus:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} W_n(x) = a_n(t) E_n W_n(x) \text{ or } a_n(t) = \exp(-iE_n t) \quad ((12))$$

Thus, $\exp(i \text{Action})$ is also $\sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x)$. Adding a factor of $W^*(y)$ i.e.

$\sum_n \exp(-iE_n t) W_n(x) W^*(y)$ yields a propagator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we start with a free particle $\exp(i \text{Action})$ i.e. $\exp(i \int_{X(T)}^{X(t)} \frac{1}{2m} \dot{X}^2 dt)$ and find that $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{Action}) = E \exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i\hbar \frac{d}{dX} \exp(i \text{Action}) = p \exp(i \text{Action})$. Using this in an energy conservation equation yields the Schrodinger equation. We propose adding a potential term $V(x)$ and investigate whether the full $\exp(i \text{Action})$ i.e. $\exp\{i \int_{X(T)}^{X(t)} [\frac{1}{2m} \dot{X}^2 - V(X(t))] dt\}$ yields a solution. We find that it does with X and T being treated as independent variables while differentiation occurs. After differentiation, we apply $A(T)=X$. We note that because X and $A(T)$ are not held equal during differentiation, one considers fluctuations while taking the derivatives. Thus, for the Schrodinger equation one seeks: $i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} \text{object} = \frac{d}{dX} \text{object} \frac{d}{dX} \text{object} (-\frac{1}{2m}) + V(x)$ and $\exp(i \text{Action}) = \text{object}$ leads to this result.

References

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